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**Industry-oriented Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory (WiSPr)
as part of the MINT^{grün} orientation studies at TU Berlin**

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INTRODUCTION

Since 2012, the Technische Universität Berlin offers a special orientation program in the subjects of mathematics, informatics, science and technologies (MINT^{gruen}; English: STEM^{green2}). It is a one-year program, which is designed to help high school graduates to find the right study course and prepare them for their later studies. Students can choose between regular MINT subjects and specially developed MINT^{gruen} laboratories. After two semesters the students can decide, which study course they want to continue with. Gained ECTS of completed subjects, which fit into the chosen study course, are considered.

The department of Fluid System Dynamics at the TU Berlin contributes to the orientation of young students by offering two different project laboratories dealing with fluid mechanics in applied mechanical engineering: The “*Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory (FMPL)*” introduced in 2017 [1] and 2018 [8] at SEFI as well as a newly designed “*Industry-oriented Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory (WiSPr³)*” covered in this paper.

Both laboratories use the teaching concept of problem-based and project-based learning:

Besides many facts, problem-based learning teaches the ability to develop strategies to solve a problem.⁴

Learning as a problem-based process is executed in a specific, scope-related context. Trainees learn from an example and are able to transfer their knowledge to a new similar problem or situation.⁵

WiSPr provides fundamental engineering skills by teaching students basics of common engineering software (such as Excel, SolidWorks, Python) and guides them through advanced usage. It also imparts structured working methods and teaching the importance of sustainable engineering. Students achieve basic and advanced engineering skills (software and working methods) as well as exploring the multi-faceted nature and the importance of resource-friendly production at the example of everyday objects like coffee machines, dryers, washing machines, and dish washers. The interdisciplinary of these everyday objects is explored by many excursions to different project partners.

Since launching the projects, they have been continuously evaluated by the students. The results show a very good rating for the teaching approach and first analysis reveal that more than half of the students participating in the orientation program choose a MINT topic for their later studies.

² STEM: Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics

³ German: wirtschaftsnahes, strömungstechnisches Projektlabor; **WiSPr**

⁴ Analogously translated from [5] p. 3; Similar definitions in English can be found in [7]

⁵ Analogously translated from [6] p.18; Similar definitions in English can be found in [7]

1 OVERVIEW OF MINT^{GRUEN} (ENGLISH: STEM^{GREEN})

1.1 Structure, numbers and trends

After graduating from high school, young people have to decide what they want to do professionally. Some choose to take an apprenticeship for about 3 years, whereas others choose an academic career. German universities offer a wide range of possible study courses. Most pupils feel overwhelmed by the countless possibilities and are unsure which course to take. They are expected to decide on “the right” study course which they will be practicing for the rest of their lives. This causes a lot of pressure and makes decisions even harder. Young people feel the need to be guided. Therefore, Technische Universität Berlin launched the orientation program in 2012, MINT^{gruen}, to show graduated pupils the variety in the fields of science, technology, engineering and mathematics. Since initiating the orientation program, the numbers of participants are steadily rising (**Fig. 1**).

Fig. 1: Numbers and trends of the MINTgruen orientation program

Fig. 2 displays the contents and structure of the orientation program, which lasts two semesters. The “Scientific Window” and the “Study Program Decision” are obligate courses, where students gain all necessary information on how to orientate themselves. In the “Scientific Window” the students have to deal with current research topics in the MINT sector and discuss these in terms of sustainability and sustainable development. They share and reflect their experiences in a separated orientation course. This helps students to get a good impression of different fields and makes the decision easier. The other modules are facultative and consist of basic lectures (i.e. engineering mathematics) and so-called Project Laboratories, which are explained in the next section. After taking the two-semester program, most of the courses can be transferred to the student’s chosen course of study.

Fig. 2: Structure of MINT^{gruen} study orientation program

1.2 Project Laboratories

Above-mentioned Project Laboratories specifically designed for MINT^{gruen} students are one characteristic feature of the orientation program MINT^{gruen}. Especially in the earlier stages of study courses subjects are more theoretical. For a successful orientation, it is mandatory that students discover their practical and project related potentials. Furthermore, students have to work on projects in their future jobs too and this is a first good practice, which usually appears not until the fourth bachelor semester.

The department of Fluid System Dynamic at the TU Berlin contributes to the orientation of young students by offering a laboratory dealing with fluid mechanics in applied mechanical engineering.

2 STRUCTURE OF WISPR

Due to the nature of a study orientation program, people are going to get attracted to the university. That does not automatically mean, that studying at universities fits a person best. The majority of TU Berlins Project Laboratories contribute to the orientation of young students by using the teaching concept of research-based learning (see also [9], [10], [11]), therefore being university-oriented. For a well-balanced student orientation, there is also a need to design industry-oriented laboratories. WiSPr Laboratory is the first industry-oriented lab at TU Berlin.

2.1 Idea and scientific background

Engineers fulfil an important role in our culture. Engineers find solutions for society's changing problems in a challenging world. Engineers implement innovations, which the community depends on. All these solutions and innovations serve a greater good. Therefore, it is important to align engineering education to fulfil society's needs.

Engineering education must become relevant to the needs of the profession in a rapidly changing world and move from its current focus on engineering science to providing graduates with the expertise to responsibly apply technology to the benefit of their communities. [12, p. vi]

Most engineering study courses (i.e. mechanical engineering, civil engineering etc.) at TU Berlin do not differ from each other in the first semesters, because they do have the same lectures to impart basic knowledge. By experience, it is hard for students to abstract what this knowledge can be used for in the later study stages or in their later jobs. Consequently, young students are not able to understand their upcoming responsibility and how society will benefit from them.

The idea of WiSPr Laboratory is to create the link between study matters and society's needs. Furthermore, a connection between different engineering disciplines is created right at the beginning of their studies. A good way to fulfil employer's requirements is to design a course collaboratively and prepare students for their later jobs. Therefore, an everyday object (i.e. coffee machines, dryers, washing machines, etc.) is taken and looked at in detail. The multi-facetted engineering nature of these products is underlined and interdisciplinarity is emphasized.

2.2 Design and Execution

At the example of a washing machine paddle (**Fig. 3**), students experience development processes in the industry. Therefore, they visit research and production facilities and get to know the industrial routines. Moreover, the students apply innovative, numerical methods for flow simulation (see also **Chapter 5**). In a laboratory session, results of the simulation are compared with reality by using a test bench.

Fig. 3: Washing machine paddle inside a washing machine drum (l.) and washing machine test bench for investigation purposes (r.)

Even if it does not show, a washing machine paddle (**Fig. 3**) is one of the most complex elements inside a washing machine. Given task for the students is to simplify the washing machine drum and design their own paddles with certain chosen abilities. The whole design process is supported by different industrial project partners and research assistants. WiSPr Lab splits into five steps as illustrated in **Fig. 4**.

Fig. 4: Design process in WiSPr Lab according to problem-based learning philosophy

The first step contains motivational excursions into research and development facilities of different industrial project partners. Students gain insight on washing machine design, product life cycles, washing processes and textile testing. Time and project management skills are taught.

After understanding the purpose of washing machine paddles, students are encouraged to design their own washing machine paddles in groups of four by choosing a number of requirements their paddle has to accomplish. Students design their paddle in a way they think it would fulfil set requirements by using a 3D-CAD⁶

⁶ CAD: Computer Aided Design

software called “SolidWorks” (step 2). Afterwards, in step 3 these paddles are used for numeric fluid simulations using a smoothed particle hydrodynamics software called “DICE⁷”. The results of the simulation are used to investigate if the paddles accomplish previously defined requirements. If not, the design of the paddle is changed and iteration processes are started. **Fig. 5** shows all paddles designed in winter term 2018 after their last iteration.

Fig. 5: Paddles designed by students using a 3D-CAD software in winter term 2018 (each paddle was created to fulfil previously set requirements)

Step 4 is used to impart knowledge about product design using virtual reality and to prepare for upcoming measurements at a test bench. Therefore, an excursion to a Virtual Reality room called “CAVE” is arranged. By wearing shutter-glasses the designed paddles are projected into the room, therefore appearing 3-dimensional in front of the students. A tracking system and the rising immersive effect allow students to interact with their geometry. Furthermore, students’ paddles are put into a virtual test bench to explain upcoming (real) measurements. Step 4 is completed by executing measurements on the real test bench and comparing results with previously done simulations.

Fig. 6 compares the simulation result with test bench investigations for the blue paddle rotating counterclockwise. Looking at the vortex formed in the middle bottom, simulation and measurement show an accurate conformability.

Fig. 6: Results of numerical simulations using smoothed particle hydrodynamics (l.) showing a washing machine paddle diving into water compared to test bench investigations (r.)

⁷ For further information please visit www.dive-solutions.de

Last but not least, step 5 covers scientific writing and presentation skills. Students create templates using MS Word and MS PowerPoint, which can be used for their later study courses. The results of each group are presented in front of all MINT^{gruen} lecturers and students.

During the steps mentioned above and illustrated in **Fig. 4** several engineering skills are achieved by the students. The most important points are summarised in **Fig. 7** including duration and contents of each step.

Step	Duration	Contents	Achieved skills
1	4 weeks	Motivation and topic introduction, Interdisciplinarity in engineering, Project management	Organisation of group projects, Time management, Creating project schedules with MS Excel, Excursion into Research and Development center, Excursion into Textile Material Testing Laboratory, Connection between mechanical engineering and textile & clothing technology
2	3 weeks	Basics in Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH)	Basic knowledge in Fluid Dynamics, Proper usage of SPH-software (dive solutions' dice), Basics of post-processing software (Paraview)
3	2 weeks	Computer aided design (CAD)	Introduction into 3D modeling, Basic usage of CAD software, Advanced usage of CAD tools (scripts & macros), Manufacturing of student's washing machine paddle
4	3 weeks	Measurement techniques, test stands and virtual reality	Purpose of test, Product design by using virtual reality, Usage of sensors, Measurement of each group's paddle, Advanced usage of MS Excel (graphs, functions)
5	3 weeks	Writing and presentation skills	Creating templates for MS Word, Basic usage of MS PowerPoint, Scientific writing recommendations

Fig. 7: Contents and achieved skills in WiSPr Laboratory

3 RESULTS AND TEACHING APPROACH

Analysis reveal that more than half of the students participating in the orientation program in 2018 choose a MINT topic for their later studies (**Fig. 8**).

Fig. 8: Number of students considering a MINT related study course at TU Berlin

Even students who leave the university and start an apprenticeship consider the contents of WiSPr as useful for their later jobs. The WiSPr Laboratory as a whole was rated in the winter term 2018 with “very good” (Fig. 9). Despite the simulation part (advanced numerical fluid mechanics) students consider WiSPr Laboratory equally difficult compared to other courses attended (Fig. 10).

Fig. 9: Students’ overall rating of WiSPr Laboratory in the winter term 2018

Fig. 10: Students’ difficulty rating of WiSPr Laboratory compared to other courses in the winter term 2018

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Whereas lectures mostly use frontal teaching methods the Project Laboratories focus on practical tasks and give students the possibility to create a STEM-related object on their own. The teaching concept of this Industry-oriented Project Laboratory contributes highly to the orientation of our students. A huge field of fluid mechanical engineering is covered. Students gain a diversified insight on fluid mechanic related topics and their field of appliance. Due to the practical concept of the laboratory students achieve various engineering skills and working methods which can be used in many study courses, apprenticeships, or even in their later jobs. Due to the

teaching of basic and advanced skills regarding engineering software (Python programming language, MS Excel, MS Word, MS PowerPoint, SolidWorks), students are well prepared for their course of study. In this program students get supported in general studying related aspects as well as fluid mechanics related topics.

5 APPENDIX – SMOOTHED PARTICLE HYDRODYNAMICS (SPH)

Smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) belongs to the meshfree methods in computational fluid dynamics (CFD). Whilst traditional CFD uses grids to solve numerical fluid dynamics, the simulation method Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics approximates fluids as an accumulation of particles moving freely in space. Every particle can be seen as a moving interpolation point. The physical field can thus be evaluated at those points by interpolating the properties of surrounding particles (see **Fig. 11**). This eliminates the need for grid generation and easily solves some of the most challenging cases of fluid mechanics. SPH efficiently solves multiphase and free surface flows, as well as moving machinery (such as gear boxes lubrication or mixing tanks). Many use cases are shown below (see **Fig. 12**).

Fig. 11: Decreasing influence of a particle (center) on its direct neighbours

Fig. 12: Extraction of use cases for Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics
 Gear box lubrication (top l.), fluidic oscillator (top r.),
 sewer system (bottom l.), sedimentation transport (bottom r.)

Feel very welcome to visit www.dive-solutions.de for more information.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Strauch, M. Muehlbauer, K. Schmermbeck und P. U. Thamsen, „MINTgruen-Fluid Mechanics Project Laboratory: Supporting and preparing students for their courses of study,“ in *Proceedings of the 45th SEFI Annual Conference 2017, Education Excellence for Sustainability*, Acores, Portugal, 2017.
- [2] L. Huber und F. Schneider, „Forschendes Lernen im Studium,“ Bielefeld, Universitätsverlag Webler, 2009, pp. 9-35.
- [3] Bargel, T (2015), Studieneingangsphase und heterogene Studentenschaft – neue Angebote und ihr Nutzen, *Hefte zur Bildungs- und Hochschulforschung*, pp. 23-30.
- [4] Felder, R., Brent, R. (2005), Understanding Student Differences. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 94: 57-72, p 60.
- [5] Paff, Marko; Problemorientiertes Lernen; Chapman & Hall; Weinheim; 1996
- [6] Zumbach, Jörg; Weber, Agnes; Olsowski, Gunter; Problembasiertes Lernen – Konzepte, Werkzeuge und Fallbeispiele aus dem deutschsprachigen Raum; h.e.p. Verlag; 2007
- [7] Valenzuela-Valdés, J. (2015). *Project based learning on engineering : Foundations, applications and challenges* (Education in a competitive and globalizing world).

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- [8] Strauch, C.; Bölter, Ch.; Thamsen, P.U. (2018): Upgrade of the MINTgruenFluid Mechanics Project Laboratory (SEFI 2017). In: *Proceedings of the 46th SEFI Annual Conference 2018 - Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence*; Copenhagen – Denmark; ISBN 978-287352-016-8

 - [9] Born, S. (2015): Annual Conference of the European Society for Engineering Education 2015 (SEFI 2015): A mathematical Lab for undergraduates, 29.6. - 2.7. 2015 in Orléans (F).

 - [10] Rademacher, L. et. Al. (2015): Annual Conference of the European Society for Engineering Education 2015 (SEFI 2015): Creativity and Construction as part of the orientation programme MINTgrün, 29.6. - 2.7. 2015 in Orléans (F).

 - [11] Schmitt, F. J. et- Al. (2017): Annual Conference of the European Society for Engineering Education 2017 (SEFI 2017): Self-dependent students in transdisciplinary projects tend to higher interest in sustainability research, 18. – 21.9. 2017 in Azores (P), pp. 25-32

 - [12] Beanland, David and Hadgraft, Roger. *Engineering education: Transformation and innovation* [online]. Melbourne, Vic.: RMIT University Press, 2013. Melbourne, Vic.: RMIT University Press, 2013. xii, 196 p. ISBN 9781922016096.